

Energy recovery system for treated wood

The Finnish wood impregnation industry is a pioneer in organizing the recovery of (impregnated) wood. Impregnated wood waste generated in households can be brought free of charge to collection points of building materials stores and waste facilities. A waste treatment fee is charged for all industrial returns. Impregnated wood is safely utilized for energy in combustion plants specializing in the treatment of impregnated wood. A non-profit company is working merely to cover the costs of recovery. The operation is funded through recycling fees.

Regional coverage and transferability

Finland has an internationally unique collection and recovery system of impregnated wood for households and companies. Decommissioned wood must not be burned in home fireplaces but must be delivered to the impregnated wood collection points of timber stores or waste facilities.

The network is transferable in other European region if similar support for the cooperation in networks is available and the use of treated wood is on a reasonable level.

Image: The Finnish Wood Preserving Association

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Impregnated wood is a recoverable product that can be used for energy production by burning it in approved industrial incinerators.
- ▶ According to Finnish national environmental legislation, impregnated wood using creosote, CCA and Cu compounds are a separately collected waste.
- ▶ Recovery provides consumers and industrial participants with an effortless and practical way to dispose of excess impregnated wood.
- ▶ The network supports companies' compliance with their obligations under EU REACH to identify and manage the risks linked to the chemical substances used in impregnated wood.
- ▶ Recycling terminals and waste treatment plants across Finland receive waste wood from companies and specialised organisations.
- ▶ Direct transportation to the recycling company's recycling terminal is usually the most economical way to return decommissioned impregnated wood and guarantees the positive public perception.